

**22NRM03 “Metrology to support standardization of hydrogen fuel sampling
for heavy duty hydrogen transport.”**

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Review on Hydrogen Refuelling Station Parameters Used in Direct Gas Sampling

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Summary

The decarbonisation of the transportation sector is crucial for meeting net-zero targets. Fuel Cell Electric Vehicles (FCEVs) running on hydrogen offer a promising solution, with hydrogen quality being critical for FCEV performance. This study focuses on the offline analysis of hydrogen quality, explicitly highlighting the critical parameters of hydrogen sampling. The aim is to review current state-of-the-art hydrogen sampling parameters, identify patterns, and propose a more accurate and representative approach for standardisation while minimising hazards. The study involved a comprehensive state-of-the-art review using an online questionnaire on the parameters used for hydrogen sampling by five sampling stakeholders. The findings provide detailed insights into each parameter, identifying trends in parameter configuration, including pressure, venting, flow rate, and temperature. The outcome of this work revealed the overtly unstandardised nature of the hydrogen sampling process. State-of-the-art reviews also provide knowledge of hydrogen sampling, insights into possibly establishing an internationally accepted, efficient, and safe method, and help transition towards a decarbonised transportation sector.

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1 Introduction

The transportation sector's decarbonisation is crucial for meeting Europe's net-zero targets. Fuel Cell Electric Vehicles (FCEVs) offer a promising solution for transportation decarbonisation as they generate electricity using hydrogen fuel cells to power the electrical engine, emit only water and heat [1]. However, hydrogen quality is critical for FCEV performance [2]. The international standard ISO 14687:2019³ and EN 17124:2022 [4] set limits for 14 contaminants in the hydrogen matrix [3]. Two main methods for analysing hydrogen are online and offline analysis, as outlined in ISO 19880-1:2020 [5]. Online analysis entails the real-time measurement of hydrogen purity. However, there is solution to measure all 14 contaminants with online analysers; on the other hand, offline analysis offers the advantage of accessing a state-of-the-art analytical laboratory able to measure all contaminants accurately. Offline analysis requires a four-step process of capturing, storing, transporting and analysing hydrogen purity in an offsite laboratory. The current study focuses on the offline analysis of hydrogen, explicitly highlighting the crucial parameters of hydrogen sampling.

Hydrogen sampling can be realised through two different sampling strategies, referred to as series and parallel strategies. Series sampling collects samples directly from a hydrogen refuelling station (HRS), while parallel sampling collects samples while refuelling an FCEV or an equivalent buffer tank [6]. Specialised sampling devices capture and store samples in cylinders, which are then transported to physical laboratories for analysis [6]. A recent literature review from Arrhenius et al. [6] emphasises the importance of sample representativeness and safety during sampling, particularly for assessing strategies for sampling hydrogen at refuelling stations for purity assessment. It is important to note that while several strategies and procedures for hydrogen sampling in HRS exist, no globally accepted method has been developed yet [6]. Series sampling is largely used worldwide, mainly in North America, Japan, or France. The series sampling strategy is realised with the HRS in maintenance mode. Therefore, it is critical to understand how the conditions used for the sampling can affect the hydrogen fuel sample. As the maintenance mode enables the HRS operator to set parameters, a survey of sampling experts worldwide was realised to gather best practice and expert knowledge to define the current state of the art of series sampling.

2 State-of-The-Art Review.

The realisation of direct sampling is standardised in North America through the ASTM D7606-17 [7]. The standard specified to set an inlet pressure of 6.9 MPa. Several sampling intercomparisons were realised [9], but the information on the exact pressure requested, storage bank, and flowrate is not

often available. Therefore, it is difficult to evaluate the actual impact of the pressure on the samples obtained. A recent study from project 19ENG04 MetroHyVE 2 showed that a side effect of pressure definition might be the definition of a specific storage bank to provide the hydrogen sample compared to filling protocol taking samples from various storage banks [8]. Storage banks may impact the hydrogen sample if they are not all equivalent. The same study did not see a correlation between flow rate and sampling protocol differences. For series sampling, the flow rate may be limited by the system's ability to fill the cylinder, and it may be manually set through the presence of a needle valve. Therefore, the actual flow rate from the HRS is not impacting the sampling. The temperature of the gas is not often referred to in the literature; however, in the study of 19ENG04 MetroHyVe 2, the actual temperature of the series sampling gas was higher than for parallel sampling (set to $-40\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$) and potentially leading to a difference in the water amount fraction [8]. In a second study (not published), the HRS gas was cooled further prior to series sampling, and a better agreement was obtained with parallel sampling. Therefore, the temperature of the gas may affect the actual sample obtained. Hydrogen venting prior to serial sampling is varying depending on the sampling system and practices. For example, ASTM D7606-17 recommend at least 1 kg venting [7], while in other studies, it is 10 times the volume of the sampling device [6] or a series of 10 cycling purges at 18 MPa [9]. The purging or venting aspect relies on the system's design. Another important aspect related of purging is obtaining a sample from the system and not from a part of the system; it is a known aspect to avoid residual gases in the proximity of the sampling point to bias the result. As the series sampling is sampled in a small volume and directly, it is possible that residual gases could affect the samples if insufficient purging is not applied.

3 Expert knowledge and best practice

A review of the industry's best practices was carried out using an online questionnaire to gather information on the parameters for direct or series sampling hydrogen at HRS. The questionnaire, described in detail in Annex A, was distributed to more than eight stakeholders, and five responses were received from stakeholders involved in direct sampling. The review was conducted on a parameter basis, revealing trends in parameter configuration, such as pressure, venting, flow rate, and temperature.

3.1 Direct sampling exercises experience

The survey assessed the current level of experience of direct sampling operations in heavy-duty (HD) and light-duty (LD) HRS (see Table 1). First, the responses received were from real experts in series sampling with a cumulative experience of over 65 samplings at LD HRS. Specifically, three out of five stakeholders conducted over 20 sampling operations at LD HRS. The survey revealed that more direct sampling operations had been carried out at LD HRS than at HD HRS. Considering that the number of HD HRS is limited worldwide compared to the LD HRS, it was an expected result. Only one out of five stakeholders conducted over 20 sampling operations at HD HRS. The results showed that series sampling system can perform sampling at HD HRS and have been doing it for some time to achieve already more than 20 realisations. In comparison, there is no known parallel sampling system able to perform HD HRS sampling until the beginning of this project.

Table 1. Survey responses for direct sampling exercises performed.

Stakeholders	SH1	SH2	SH3	SH4	SH5
How many direct sampling exercises have you performed from light-duty HRS?	-	6-20	>20	>20	>20
How many direct sampling exercises have you performed from heavy-duty HRS?	-	<6	6-20	-	>20

3.2 Best practices on pressure during series sampling

The operation of direct sampling requires the HRS to be into maintenance mode. Therefore, the series sampling can't follow a filling protocol and the pressure ramp. In maintenance mode, the delivery of gas is controlled by an HRS operator. The delivery pressure can therefore be set for the sampling, however there is no standardised requirement for it. The survey was investigating the current practices. The survey data in Table 2 reveals that most stakeholders conduct sampling operations at a set pressure either 35 MPa or 70 MPa, depending on the size of the HRS nozzle. This data also suggests that the sampling team are responsible for determining the sampling pressure in 80% of the cases.

Table 2. Survey responses for pressure parameter and strategy.

Stakeholders	SH1	SH2	SH3	SH4	SH5
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Who sets the sampling pressure?	HRS operator	Sampling Team and HRS Operator	HRS operator	HRS operator	HRS Operator
What level of pressure is set during standard sampling?	70 MPa for H70 nozzle or 35MPA for H35 nozzle	~35MPa	70 MPa for H70 nozzle or 35MPA for H35 nozzle	Sampling Team and HRS Operator	70 MPa for H70 nozzle or 35MPA for H35 nozzle

However, there is a deviation from this trend in the case of SH4, where a more flexible approach is taken to define the sampling pressure. In this instance, the HRS operator and the sampling team decide the sampling pressure on a case-by-case basis and probably deviate from the other sampling experts' 35 or 70 MPa conditions. This variation may be due to the specific HRS facility or the need to accommodate different pressure rating designs for various sampling devices.

The survey results showed a difference between the ASTM D7606-17 and the current sampling practices. The pressure identified are 6.9, 35 and 70 MPa being mostly used.

3.3 Flow rate

Flow rate is a dynamic parameter during the FCEV filling. It is not often required but monitored in function of the pressure set and sampling system capacity. However, a standardised operational limit (maximum flow rate delivered by HRS: 60 g/s for light duty and 120 g/s for heavy duty) is required to ensure all sampling operations are conducted safely [6]. This ensures the sampling flow rate does not exceed the sampling devices' ratings. The survey indicates an unestablished hydrogen sampling flow rate. Most stakeholders suggested that the flow rate was not set, and a common trend of pressure-based flow was observed. This pressure-based flow may be defined as the resulting flow rate from a determined sampling pressure. However, SH1 and SH4 indicated that the Sampling Team and HRS Operator set the flow rate with no definite value assigned to the flow rate during hydrogen sampling. According to current practices, the flow rate is not a parameter set, but it may be monitored. Therefore, it is difficult to define any trend in the current practice for this parameter.

Table 3. Survey responses for flow rate parameter and strategy.

Stakeholders	SH1	SH2	SH3	SH4	SH5
Who sets the sampling flow rate?	Sampling Team	Pressure based	HRS operator	Sampling Team	HRS Operator
What level of flow is set during standard sampling?	Sampling Team and HRS Operator	Not set	Not set	Sampling Team and HRS Operator	Not set

3.4 Temperature

The temperature is an important parameter to quickly refill a FCEV. Therefore, it may not be considered critical for the series sampling system as no FCEV is refilled. Several temperatures may be used during refuelling (ambient, T20: -20 °C or T40: -40 °C), it depends on the type of vehicles and the expected duration of the refuelling. Currently the SAE J2601 [10] document refers to T40, T30, T20 and for future revision to T10 and ambient. It is part of the parameters that can be set during a series sampling event.

Table 4 Survey Responses for temperature parameter and strategy

Stakeholders	SH1	SH2	SH3	SH4	SH5
Who sets the sampling temperature?	HRS operator	Sampling Team and HRS Operator	HRS operator	-	HRS operator
What level of temperature is set during standard sampling?	Ambient	T40 or T20	No modification of temperature	-	H70 -40°C (Ambient H35)

The sampling system should be designed to accommodate the hydrogen fuel temperature from 60 °C down to -40 °C to ensure the safe handling of hydrogen [6]. According to the survey conducted in the present work, SH2 and SH5 have adopted temperatures of -20°C and -40°C, as displayed in Table 4. They are setting the temperature to the expected hydrogen temperature during a FCEV refill. SH3

information may be interpreted as following the same approach as SH2 and SH5 in using the same temperature as for a normal FCEV refill. On the other hand, SH1, which uses ambient temperature, deviates from the practices of other experts. The survey highlighted a sort of consensus on using the hydrogen gas temperature during a refill (i.e., T40, T20), whereas another expert would use an ambient temperature sampling. It would be important to compare the results from the different temperatures to determine if one temperature is suitable (ambient) or if the actual refuelling temperature should be applied.

3.5 Venting rate and flow rate

To ensure sample representativeness in hydrogen sampling procedures, it is a common practice to purge the sampling devices with multiple cycles of hydrogen flow and vent them into the atmosphere [6].

Table 5 Survey responses for venting volume, flowrate and strategy

Stakeholders	SH1	SH2	SH3	SH4	SH5
Is there a specific volume of hydrogen vented before sampling?	~0.5kg	Pressure cycle purge rather than volume	<1 kg	~0.0018kg	0.2kg gaseous sampling, not particulate
Can you provide an estimate of the venting flow rate of your sampling system?	0.017kg/min	~0.6kg/min	No flow control for the vent	-	0.4 kg/min

ASTM standard D7606:17 recommended venting up to 1 kg of hydrogen to ensure an optimum system purge before sampling activity [7]. However, the survey adopted in the present work reveals a somewhat inconsistent variation in volume vented and flow rate during venting, with values ranging from 0.0018 kg to 1 kg, indicating the variability of practice across experts. The purging volume may need to be reported in the function of the sampling system's internal volume to be able to compare different systems. However, it would be important to determine how the purging volume may affect the actual sample obtained. Therefore, no purging and large purging (as 1 kg) are important

experiments to understand its importance better. The absence of control and monitoring instruments installed on sampling devices makes it difficult to evaluate flow rates.

4 Conclusion

Based on the report, there is several parameters that are non-standardized and could significantly affect the sample representativity as the temperature, the pressure, and venting rates. The flow rate doesn't seem like a parameter set and mostly a consequence of the setting of the other parameters.

To develop a standard, there is a need to understand how these parameters would affect the sampling. Therefore, the report identified few pressures (6.9 MPa, 20 MPa and 35 MPa if possible 70 MPa) as potential pressure of interest. For the temperature, there is few conditions of interest: ambient, T20, T30, T40 and potentially T10. For the purging, it is more complex due to the actual system volume and HRS residual gases however few conditions may be relevant: no purging, 0.2 kg, 0.5 kg and 1 kg. It would be recommended to refer to a mass in relationship to the actual sampling system internal volume. A last parameter of importance is the ability to realise a sampling without entering the maintenance mode, therefore the ability to sample from the HRS pressure pulse or the bias associated in this realisation should be investigated for further standardisation and definition of best practices for series sampling at HRS nozzle.

Future work may compare sample representativeness after applying stated parameters and procedures after the study of the above-mentioned criteria. Standardisation of sampling parameters is crucial to ensure the consistency and reliability of results obtained from hydrogen sampling in HRS. Developing a globally accepted hydrogen sampling method is necessary to promote safety, accuracy, and efficiency in the field. This report offers valuable insights for stakeholders in hydrogen sampling. It serves as a starting point for future research and development in this area with the ultimate goal of advancing the use of hydrogen as a clean and sustainable energy source.

5 References

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Annex A - Questionnaire

The question in the present work focused on the significant parameters and their operating levels during direct sampling operations.

1. How many direct sampling exercises have you performed?

- a) Light-duty HRS (<6, 6 to 20, >20)
- b) Heavy duty HRS (<6, 6 to 20, >20)

For direct sampling of hydrogen fuel, several parameters may need to be defined, can you fill to the best of your experience the information below:

2. Pressure:

a) Is the pressure set by (select one of the responses below):

- i. HRS operator
- ii. Sampling team
- iii. Others (please add details)

b) what level of pressure is set during standard sampling:

- i. Maximum operating pressure: 70 MPa for H70 nozzle for example or 35MPa for H35
- ii. specific pressure defined by the sampling team or the HRS operator
- iii. Others (please add details)

3. Flow:

a. Is the flow set by (select one of the responses below):

- i. HRS operator
- ii. sampling team
- iii. Others (please add details)

b. what level of flow is set during standard sampling:

- i. Not set
- ii. ii. Specific flow rate defined by the sampling team or the HRS operator
- iii. Others (please add details) :

4. Temperature:

a. Is the temperature set by (select one of the responses below):

- i. HRS operator
- ii. Sampling team
- iii. Others (please add details)

b. what level of temperature is set during standard sampling:

- i. T20
- ii. T40
- iii. Ambient

- iv. specific pressure/temperature defined by the sampling team or the HRS operator
 - v. Others (please add details) : No modification of temperature
5. Venting/purging before taking sample:
- a. Is there a specific volume of hydrogen vented before sampling (select one of the responses below):
 - i. 1 kg
 - ii. No venting
 - iii. depend on the sampling system and the HRS size
 - iv. Others (please add details) : < 1 kg
 - b. venting rate, can you provide an estimate of the venting flow rate of your sampling system? No flow control for vent